

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19206429

APPLYING CURRICULUM CONTENT MAPPING (CCM) METHOD FOR CURRICULUM ASSESSMENT-JORDANIAN ARCHITECTURE CURRICULUMS CASE STUDY

Anwaar M.Banisalman^{1*}

¹Al albayt University, Faculty of Engineering, Architecture Department, Jordan,
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5045-441X>

Received: 20/11/2025
Accepted: 29/12/2025

Corresponding Anwaar M.Banisalman
(anwaarsalman@abbu.edu.jo)

ABSTRACT

The need to adapt the higher education system to the demands and expectations of the business and community sectors has prompted decision-makers to adopt more appealing strategies. Additionally, a variety of elements, including organizational culture, institutional politics, values, educational applications, external stakeholders, and educational philosophies, impact curriculum evaluation methodologies. What is the physical disparity between Jordanian and foreign architectural schemes' competencies? Approaches to curriculum evaluation are influenced by a wide range of elements, including organizational culture, institutional politics, values, instructional applications, external stakeholders, and educational philosophies. In many nations, it is observed that there is a disconnect between the academic and professional worlds of architecture because of inadequate study strategies. This study employs the curriculum mapping method to evaluate architecture engineering study plans in Jordanian universities. It concludes that this also occurs in the Jordanian case and identifies a physical imbalance in the competencies of architectural plans in Jordan when compared to international plans. The corporation of policy planners, civil society, and teachers needs to reform the curriculum to determine what is appropriate for the market and compatible with future changes. Additionally, decision-makers in the higher education system have used a variety of strategies in response to the need to change the system to better meet the demands of the business community and the community. This research insure that it is very important to apply that global perspective to the local context, to take the lessons learned and raise the standards of quality in the local experience.

KEYWORDS: Curriculum Mapping, Pedagogy, Architecture Education, Jordan, Cultural differences.

1. INTRODUCTION

Curriculum Mapping Method (CCM) is a technique used to explore how Knowledge is taught together with skills in curriculums, depending on the competency concept (The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2020). Sixteen countries participated in the CCM exercise in 2020; OECD countries are Australia, British Columbia (Canada), Estonia, Greece, Israel, Japan, Korea, Lithuania, Northern Ireland (United Kingdom), Portugal, Saskatchewan (Canada), Sweden, and partner countries: China, Kazakhstan, and Russian Federation for comparative analysis. (maart, Frantz, & Mphil, 2021) use curriculum mapping to demonstrate the alignment of an undergraduate dental curriculum with a competency framework; curriculum mapping revealed areas for improvement or gaps in the UWC dentistry curriculum's AfriMEDS competencies. (Alshanjiti, Benaida, Alam, & Namoun, 2020) use the same method as a two-dimensional matrix expressing the relationship between the student's learning outcomes and the courses.

In general, the architect plays a vital role in the overall building development process. (Andrew, 2008) both architecture and architecture engineering are professions that play a principal part in the creation of buildings; there are some essential differences between them; architecture engineering is a profession that focuses on close interaction between architecture and engineering within the building design process. There is a strong background in structural calculations and material selection, and it is professional. Architects' engineering knowledge needs structural calculations; therefore, they need engineers' expertise; it emphasizes aesthetic value and spatial organization. Both professions have a number of things in common and have a number of common courses in their study programs. In some designs, the structure of the building is the main aesthetical accent, often termed structural art. (Parasonis & Jodko, 2013). VGTU (Vilnius Gediminas Technical University) in 2002, based on the subject matter examination of undergraduate Architecture and Civil Engineer programs at present at that time at

VGTU. (Parasonis & Jodko, 2013) developed the competence model after studying the relationship between architecture and engineering as a need to get more efficient structures, see Table (1).

The selection of this model as a benchmark for competence comparison because of the following reasons:

1-Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (Vilnius Tech) is a leading higher education institution in Vilnius, Lithuania's capital. is a country in the Baltic region of Europe; established in 1956, VILNIUS TECH is one of the biggest research universities in the country, with a focus on technologies and engineering and a strong emphasis on university-business cooperation.

2-Vilnius Tech is ranked by 4 subjects in QS WUR 2020:

- #51-100 in Engineering – Civil & Structural.
- #101-150 in Architecture / Built Environment.
- Vilnius Tech is ranked in 2 broad subject areas: top #=256 Engineering & Technology, and top #=276 Social Sciences & Management.

3-This competence model is distinguished by overlapping engineering competencies with architecture competencies.

4-It is a contextual-driven model can the university used as an example by study plan developers.

5- The competence model has a clear structure: competencies, sub-competencies, and courses, where the main competencies are: personal, social, communication, professional, and research. The courses in the Vilnius curriculum are: Architectural design, Architectural drawings, Building codes, Building engineering physics, Building engineering systems, Programming presentation tools, Communication studies, Complex projects, Composition, Construction engineering, Final project, Free elective, Geodesy, History of building construction, Humanities and social studies, Industrial training, Mathematics, Natural sciences, Physical training, Professional language, Professional practice, Project management, Structural analysis, Training (Parasonis & Jodko, 2013).

Table 1: Vilnius Tech University Competence Model.

research	professional										communication			social			personal			Competences								
	Common	Common	Professional ARCH +SE	Team Management	General	ARCH+SE	ARCH+SE	SE	ARCH	ARCH+SE	ARCH+SE	specialization	common	professional visual presentation	professional documentation	general	professional	general	professional-legal	general-legal	team work-social	common-social	professional	general	sub competence			
research	customer and personal service	management	inspection	construction material and techniques	Project Development	technical knowledge	professional practice	information	communication	legal	social	continuous professional development	analytic skills	self development	basic	sub-sub competences										course label		
																										architectual design		
																											architectual drawings/graphics/artistic expression	
																											building codes	
																											building engineering phisics	
																											building engineering systems:design technology	
																											CAD,BIM,IT programming representation tools	
																											commuication studies;publicspeaking;foreign language	
																											complex project:architecture engineering	
																											composition	
																											construction engineering,inspection,quantity surveying	
																											final project :architecture,structure,urban,landscape design	
																											free elective	
																											geodesy	
																											history of building construction,architecture,arts	
																											humanities,social science	
																											industrial training:architectutre,structures	
																											mathmatics	
																											natural sciences	
																											physical training	
																											professional language	
																											professional practice	
																											project management	
																											structural analysis and design	
																											training/ practice surveynig	

A "competency" is a holistic and dynamic concept that includes Knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values. In 21 St century, there were a set of

competencies based on skills, character, Meta-learning, and knowledge forms learning objectives in the traditional curriculums at different levels, but all

in all, considering competencies must be:

- Deliberate, so it must have been considered internationally as an opportunity for learning.
- Explicit; deserve more much focus as Knowledge.
- With comprehensive, high-quality education, students can improve their skills by encountering as many competencies as possible.
- Systematic; means that the competence must be fit with the discipline.

Demonstrable; this requires designing competencies in a way that can be measurable for any assessment process. (Center for Curriculum Redesign's Research team, 2021) With reference to the above, how effectively do architecture engineering curricula in Jordanian universities align with international standards in terms of competency distribution when evaluated using the curriculum mapping method?

2. JORDANIAN ARCHITECTURE CURRICULUMS CASE STUDY

The quality of higher education outputs is the

process to verify that academic standards are compatible with the vision of the educational institution, that has been identified, defined and achieved in a manner that complies with its corresponding standards either on a national or global level and that the level of quality of learning opportunities.

The Ministry of Higher Education controls all the universities in Jordan and, subject to the National Accreditation Board, aims to reform curriculums. (Dagher, Tarawneh, & Al-Quda, 2016) their study of the Jordanian education outputs about the practice, the market found that the harmonization between them is average. Indeed, there is a gap between them (Al Wahsha, 2020).

To answer the research question: What is the physical imbalance in the competencies in the architectural plans in Jordan compared to international plans? This research uses Curriculum Content Mapping (CCM) to study AE curriculums in Jordan and uses UTV as a competency benchmark. Since we have not in Jordan a clear and specific competence model, this method requires the following process: Suggest codes A1-A24, see table2.

Table 2: Code Each Group of courses in Jordanian Curriculum's. Source: Researcher.

code	Courses
A1	Architectural design
A2	Architectural drawings/graphics/artistic expression
A3	Building codes
A4	Building engineering physics
A5	Building engineering systems: design technology
A6	CAD,BIM,IT programming representation tools
A7	Communication studies; public speaking; foreign language
A8	Complex project: architecture engineering
A9	Composition
A10	Construction engineering, inspection, quantity surveying
A11	Final project :architecture, structure, urban, landscape design
A12	Free elective
A13	Geodesy
A14	History of building construction, architecture, arts
A15	Humanities, social science
A16	Industrial training: architecture, structures
A17	Mathematics
A18	Natural sciences
A19	Physical training
A20	Professional language
A21	Professional practice
A22	Project management
A23	Structural analysis and design
A24	Training/ practice surveying

2.1. Match each course from a Jordanian university with a group of courses suggested by the UTV model, Such as:

- Building engineering physics group, the following courses: Building Construction.
- Communication studies: Communication skills, Arabic, and English.

- Humanities and Social Science: Behavior, Military Studies, Engineering Innovation, Responsibility, and National Education.
- History of buildings: Architecture Theory, History of Architecture, Urban Theory, Interior Design, and Sustainable Architecture.
- Natural Science: Physics, Chemistry, and Computer Skills. See figure 1.

Figure 1: Match Courses in Jordanian Curriculum with Group of Courses in UTV model to know the exact competence for each course. Source: Researcher.

3. Take competencies suggested by the UTV model and match them with Jordanian courses figure (2).
4. Map the gap in each study plan.

COURSES	personal				social		communication		professional				research			
	basic	self development	analytic skills	continuous professional development	social	legal	communication	information	professional practice	technical knowledge	Project Development	construction materials and techniques	inspection	management	customer and personal service	research
English Communication skills																
Architectural Technical Drawing																
Intro. to Creative Arts I																
Appreciation of Art I																
Intro. to Creative Arts II																
Computer Skills																
Social Ethics																
Military Science																
Intro. to Computer Graphics																
Cultural Development I																
Introduction to Drawing and Perspective I																
Arabic Communication Skills																
English Communication Skills II																
General Physics (I)																
Computer Aided Drafting I/ Auto CAD + 3D Max																
History of Architecture and Art I																
Computer Aided Drafting & Design																
History of Architecture and Art II																
Architectural Design Studio I																
Architectural Design Studio II																
Sports I																
Sports 2																
Computer Aided Drafting & Design																
Color Theory & Applications																
Architectural Design Studio III																
Building Construction Materials and Processes I																
Computer Aided Architectural Design I																
Structural Systems I																
Contemporary Architecture and Design																
Land Surveying																
Architectural Design Studio IV																

Figure.2: Match Competences extracted from UTV Model with Courses in Jordanian Curriculum. Source: Researcher.

The percentage of student to the total population

in Jordan, according to (Tamimi, 2015), were 1:23, which was a high ratio, 2021 increased to 1:32,

compared to German at 1:32.4, and UK 1:25.6, which ensures that Jordan is an educated population but in other hand raise in the surface the issue of employment.

graduated students in Jordan were 22664, most of whom were females; the total number of university unemployed graduates was 244292 (76%) of the total number of graduated students.

(Tamimi, 2015) Pointed out that bachelor-

Figure3.Number of undergraduate students in Jordanian at private universities by program 2012-2013. Source: (Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research , 2012/2013).

(Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2012/2013) mentioned that 66,655 students are the number of undergraduate students in Jordanian private universities program from 2012-2013. Figure (3) shows 1654 students in architecture

and planning programs; it's around 2.4 % (researcher) based on (Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, 2012/2013). Also, by looking at table (3), notes that the number of private universities has increased, so the number of students

with a bachelor's degree will form 28% of total BA students.

TOTAL	DEGREE						UNIVERSITY NAME	TYPE OF UNIVERSITY
	TECHNICAL DIPLOMA	INTERMEDIATE DIPLOMA	PHD	MASTER	HIGHER DIPLOMA	BA		
2243	529	1938	487	2423	289	2748	GRAND TOTAL	
63	0	0	0	0	0	53	Prince Hussein Academy for Civil Protection	GOVERNMENTAL
405	44	0	88	654	0	434	University of Jordan	
287	0	0	0	78	0	277	University of Jordan - Ajlun	
431	0	0	0	440	0	387	German Jordanian University	
2240	0	0	61	140	0	2224	The Hashemite University	
1175	0	0	91	203	0	931	Al al-Bayr University	
483	0	181	0	62	0	174	Balqa Applied University	
851	0	0	0	44	0	344	Al-Hussein Bin Talal University	
1655	0	45	0	28	0	236	Talita Technical University	
2634	0	0	61	167	0	2431	Jordan University Of Science and Technology	
3171	0	0	250	428	0	2591	Yarmouk University	
1923	0	0	173	26	0	36	Mutah University	
2468	44	1871	28	146	0	227	Governmental Universities TOTAL	
21	0	0	0	0	0	21	Jordanian academy for private music	PRIVATE
171	0	0	0	0	0	171	The American University of Madaba	
8	0	0	0	0	0	8	Arab University College of Technology	
272	0	0	0	21	0	251	Arab private university	
113	0	0	0	31	0	42	Al-Balqa University	
423	0	0	11	17	0	383	Princess Sumaya University of Technology	
630	0	0	0	80	0	620	Peira private university	
172	0	0	0	45	0	62	Targa Private University	
116	0	0	0	28	0	77	Al-Captounah private university of Jordan	
140	0	0	0	53	0	374	Middle East University	
149	0	0	0	0	0	25	Ajlun University of Technology	
580	0	0	0	28	0	583	private university of applied sciences	
49	0	0	0	30	0	384	Jadara University	
460	0	0	0	44	0	79	Arush private university	
238	0	0	0	22	0	81	Aqaba National Private University	
117	0	0	0	14	0	63	Al-Balqa American University	
345	0	0	0	10	0	17	Amman Arab University	
373	0	0	0	12	0	353	Philadelphia private university	
37	0	0	0	0	0	37	Al-Qadisiyah University College of Technology	
120	0	0	0	0	0	120	Faculty of Educational Sciences and Arts - UNFPA	
71	0	0	0	71	0	1	Talal Abu Ghazalah University College for Innovation	
17	0	0	0	0	0	17	Amman Applied University College	
115	0	0	0	0	0	115	Lamta Technical University College	
4	0	0	0	4	0	0	Jordanian science institute	
728	0	0	11	50	0	34	private TOTAL	
16	45	0	0	0	0	47	Al-Hussein Technical University	SPECIAL LOW
118	0	90	75	18	0	228	International University of Islamic Sciences	
128	45	90	75	18	0	228	special low TOTAL	
235	0	0	0	72	0	5	Arabic Open University	REGIONAL
245	0	0	0	72	0	5	regional TOTAL	

Table 3: Summary Of The Numbers Of Students Enrolled In Second-Degree Universities For The 2020/2021 Semester By University And Academic Degree.

3. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

There are eight public universities in Jordan and 12 private and 8 private Universities that teach AE.

There are 21 universities teaching architecture in Jordan until the date this research conducted, with two types of architecture schools (13 departments of architecture and seven colleges of architecture). In

terms of degrees, there are two types (6 architecture and 14 architecture engineering), see table (4).

Table 4: Classification of Architecture Schools in Jordan. D: Department,C:College, AE: Architecture Engineering, A : Architecture, G:Governmental University, P: Private University.

	University name	Architecture school College/Department	Pedagogy type AE/A	Private/Governmental/S pecial low
1	University of Jordan	D	AE	G
2	Jordan University of Science and Technology	C	A	G
3	Yarmouk University	D	AE	G
4	Hashemite University	D	AE	G
5	Albalqa Applied University	D	AE	G
6	Philadelphia University at Jordan	D	AE	P
8	AlAl-Bayt University	D	AE	G
9	Muta University	D	AE	G
10	University of Petra	C	A	P
11	Middel East University Jordan	C	A	P
12	Applied Science University	D	AE	P
13	German Jordanian University	C	A	G
14	Al Zaytoonah University	C	A	P
15	Al Ahliyya Amman University	C	AE	P
16	Zarqa University	D	AE	P
17	Amman Arab University	D	AE	P
18	American University of Madaba	C	AE	P
19	Al Isra Private University Amman	D	AE	P
20	Jerash university	D	AE	P
21	Al aqaba university for technology	D	AE	P

Researcher conduct a CCM analysis approach related to the UTV model to answer the first question according to the following aspects:

1. Computerized courses, digital design courses.
2. Competences, group of courses.
3. Curriculum characteristics.

The Researcher collected all the curriculums from 13 architecture engineering schools at Jordanian universities and mapped the computer courses and digital design courses in university, college, and department compulsory courses. Analys shows that (0-6%) of the study plan in AE are separate courses that teach computer science as stand-alone courses ;(2DCAD,3D CAD, C++, GIS), and there are no digital design studios as separated courses.Using CCM referenced to UTV University AE Competence, the outcomes mapping methodology aims to be an evidence-based method of curriculum evaluation

and development, see figure (4) ,for Al albayt University as an example; for other universities; we find the main defects:

Comparing the main competencies, Personal, social, communication, professional, and research, two universities (Alabayt University and Amman arab university) do not meet some competencies; there is a lack of (continuous professional development) sub-sub competence in personal competence, this define the emerging patterns in competences. Even if all the qualification requirements are met (continuous professional development), the rest of the universities remained within simple limits, Albalqa University and Mota University, also group of courses:(Complex project: architecture engineering) and(Composition) were not fulfilled in the study plans in all universities; here, a prominent and clear difference appears

between local and international study plans.

In general, there are differences between

universities in the number of credit hours and courses taught, even within the same competence.

	Al-Abdali university													
	personal			social		communication			professional					
	self development	social focus	professional development	social	legal	communication	information	professional practice	technical knowledge	Project Development	communication and leadership	innovation	entrepreneur	social career and personal activities
مدخل إلى التصميم المعماري 1														
الرسم الحر 1														
الرسم الحر 2														
الجزء العام 1														
الجزء العام العمل 1														
مدخل هندسة														
الرسم والاطوار المعماري 1														
مدخل إلى التصميم المعماري 2														
الرسم الهندسي و تطبيقاته في العمارة														
تفصيل و تكامل 1														
مطلب جامعة الجزائر														
تفصيل و تكامل 2														
التصميم المعماري 2														
التاريخ والتراث المعماري 1														
التاريخ المعماري 1														
التاريخ والتراث المعماري 2														
التصميم المعماري 2														
تطبيقات الحاسوب														
مبادئ الاتصال و الكتابة العلمية														
التاريخ المعماري 2														
مبادئ المساحة نظرية العمارة														
التصميم المعماري 3														
ميكانيكا الإنشاء														
المساحة الحديثة														
الأنظمة الصخرية بالحديقة المنزلية														
تأثيرات في التصميم الداخلي														
التصميمات الخارجية														
العمارة المعاصرة														
العمارة الاستوائية														
مطلب تخصصي اختياري														
نظريات التصميم الحضري														
مطلب تخصصي اختياري														
التصميم المعماري 4														
مطلب تخصصي اختياري														
مطلب جامعة الجزائر														
تصميم عمارة 3														
تصميم عمارة اختيارية عمارة 3														
التحكم البيئي														
هندسة التبريد والتدفئة														
الانظمة و الصناعات														
القواعد الهندسية														
انظمة البناء وممارسة المهنة														
الطرق والتقنيات و حسابات الكلفة														
مطلب تخصصي اختياري														
مطلب جامعة الجزائر														
التدريب الهندسي														
التخطيط الحضري و الاسكان														
بحث مشروع التخرج														
تصميم مشروع التخرج														
مطلب تخصصي اختياري														

Figure 5. Sample Of Study Plan -Competence.

To visualize the methodology of this research, to be used by any educational institution or researches,

see figure 6.

Figure 6. Methodology to Create of Contextual Competence Model. Source: Researcher

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RESULTS

There is a need to reverse the study plans according to era needs; this is a digital era, and emerging computer skills and programs raised to the surface. Also, higher education cannot unify the required Architecture skills or competencies, and they must consider the type of work the architect must fill.

Digital architecture from this time into the future is not a course used by some computer programs for presentation or model making; instead, it's more profound discipline means that digital skills are well integrated with study plan courses as it serves the course goal and enhances student competencies. And there is a defined need to develop curriculums to meet accreditation criteria and standards for students' performance SPCs.

There is a need to change the stereotypical social view of applied disciplines and emphasizing the role of technicians and technicians in various engineering fields to accommodate and provide them with a broader opportunity in the local, regional, and global labor market taking in to consideration that

Professional competence is not just for some courses but depends on overlapping between courses such as training and design, management, and communication skills. So engineering education sector should develop itself humanly, institutionally, and legally through the following:

1. Adopt a strategic planning method for the development of university education institutions.
2. Determining enrollment opportunities in university engineering education programs and community awareness
3. And new students do so.
4. Improve the outputs of engineering education in line with the requirements of development and the labor market.
5. Improve the level of internal efficiency of university education institutions.
6. Develop the human resources (faculty members and their assistants).
7. Improve the educational environment.
8. Develop all the information and communication technology in the service of the educational process.
9. Develop the role of postgraduate studies and

- raise their level.
10. Encourage research institutions to enter the world of scientific research strongly.
 11. Adopt a strategic planning method for the development of university education institutions according to differences in culture.
 12. Determining enrollment opportunities in university engineering education programs and community awareness and new students do so.
 13. Improve the outputs of engineering education in line with the requirements of development and the labor market.
 14. Improve the level of internal efficiency of university education institutions.
 15. Develop the human resources (faculty members and their assistants).
 16. Improve the educational environment.
 17. Develop all the information and communication technology in the service of the educational process.
 18. Develop the role of postgraduate studies and raise their level.
 19. Encourage research institutions to enter the world of scientific research strongly.

Acknowledgements: We thank the reviewers for their constructive comments.

REFERENCES

- Alshantqiti, A., Benaida, M., Alam, T., & Namoun, A. (2020). *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(12).
- Al Wahsha, R. (2020). Towards an ambitious engineering education. *JEA Magazine*, 34–37.
- Andrew, S. (2008). *Architect and Engineer: A Study in Sibling Rivalry*. Yale University Press.
- Center for Curriculum Redesign's Research Team. (2021). *Embedding competencies within disciplines*. Center for Curriculum Redesign.
- Maart, R., Frantz, J. M., & Mphil, A. R. (2021). Curriculum mapping: A tool to align competencies in a dental curriculum. *Journal Name*, 13(2).
- Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research. (2012/2013). *Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research statistics in Jordan*.
- Parasonis, J., & Jodko, A. (2013). Competence model for the architectural engineering professional. *Procedia Engineering*, 876–881.
- Tamimi, A. (2015). Higher education in Jordan: Crisis & opportunities. *The Fifth PRME MENA Forum*, Amman.
- The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2020). *Technical report: Curriculum analysis of the OECD Future of Education and Skills 2030*. OECD.